

COcyber success stories

Hungary case study on cybersecurity technology and information transfer

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To understand how cybersecurity ecosystems evolve across Europe, COcyber conducted four national case studies focusing on Lithuania, Spain, Hungary, and Slovenia.

The studies, brought together in a **comparative booklet**, examined:

- Governance structures
- Technology transfer
- Information-sharing mechanisms
- Dual-use cybersecurity potential

In this context, **Hungary** shows how cybersecurity technology and information transfer are shaped by a system where state coordination, legal frameworks, and defence priorities play a central role. The case also shows that progress depends on stronger links between regulation, innovation, practical cooperation, and civilian–defence exchange

NATIONAL CYBERSECURITY LANDSCAPE

Hungary's cybersecurity landscape is shaped by strong state coordination and a governance model closely aligned with national security and defence priorities. Recent strategic and legal developments, including the new national cybersecurity strategy and the renewal of the legal environment, have strengthened the formal framework for cyber defence. At the same time, the case points to uneven implementation and differing perceptions between state and market actors on how effectively the system works in practice.

TECHNOLOGY TRANSFER FRAMEWORK

The Hungarian case shows that technology transfer is recognised as important for strengthening national security, critical infrastructure protection, and long-term cooperation between civilian and military actors. However, the framework remains constrained by regulatory ambiguity, bureaucratic barriers, and limited institutional support for turning innovation into wider operational use.

INFORMATION-SHARING PRACTICES

Hungary has developed institutional mechanisms for cybersecurity information sharing, including the National Cyber Security Centre, mandatory reporting channels, and cooperation linked to cyber defence exercises. However, the case also highlights persistent barriers, particularly mistrust beyond public administration, fragmented cooperation across sectors, and the lack of common platforms and shared practices.

DUAL-USE POTENTIAL

The case presents dual-use technologies as an important part of Hungary's cyber defence model, especially where civilian and military needs overlap in areas such as secure communications, incident management, and critical infrastructure protection. At the same time, the case shows that dual-use development is understood differently across sectors, with stronger emphasis from the defence side and a more cautious, innovation-focused view from market actors.

RECOMMENDATION HIGHLIGHT

Hungary's next step is to build stronger trust across the ecosystem, reduce barriers around technology transfer, improve cross-sector information sharing, and create clearer conditions for the development and uptake of dual-use cybersecurity technologies.